

Comparative effects from treatments revealed that the maximum temperature in day-night combination temperatures was crucial in determining the sterility or fertility of TGMS lines. The effects of intervening fertility-inducing temperature (27 °C) during the sterility phase (32/24 °C) were studied in TGMS lines IR68945-4-33-4-14, ID24, and Norin PL 12. Even an exposure for 2 h at 27 °C could induce fertility in IR68945-4-33-4-14, whereas ID24 remained unaffected even after 10 h exposure at 27 °C. The behavior of Norin PL 12 was intermediate in this respect as 4 h of interruption could induce fertility. ■

Identifying and characterizing thermosensitive cytoplasmic male sterile lines

A. J. Ali, Crop Improvement Department, Agriculture College and Research Institute, Navalur Kuttapattu, Trichy 620009; E. A. Siddiq, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi 110001; F. U. Zaman, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012; and M. I. Ahmed, Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad 500030, India

In wheat, an alloplasmic line of Norin 26 (*Triticum aestivum*) with *Aegilops crassa* cytoplasm has been found to show male sterility under long-day (15.0 h) conditions and fertility under short-day (14.5 h) conditions with no influence of temperature. In the present study, a similar influence of temperature rather than photoperiod was observed in wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line J24A (Pusa 33-16A). It was studied along with its maintainer line J24B (Pusa 33-16B) under different temperature regimes for fertility-sterility alterations. The pattern of their fertility-sterility transformation revealed them to be of high critical sterility point (CSP) and high critical fertility point (CFP) type. Yet they differed in their degree of transformation; the CSP was 33.8 °C in J24A and 35.1 °C in J24B. Although the

CFPs of both fall in the same range (24-28 °C), a comparative study of the A and B lines for their temperature-influenced sterility-fertility behavior revealed the thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) gene to be probably linked to the nuclear sterility gene (*rf*). Fertile cytoplasm (C gene) also possessed some degree of influence on fertility as well as on TGMS genes located in the nuclear genome. This was evident from the B line, which showed a relatively higher CSP and CFP than the A line. To have a stable CMS line, the nuclear genome should have the fertility gene *Rf* with the environment-sensitive male sterility gene (EGMS) in a dominant state, so that neither temperature nor daylength would affect its stability for pollen sterility. A CMS line having the

EGMS gene in a recessive state can be deployed under high-temperature conditions for hybrid seed production. The A line in this state will be more stable for sterility because of the combined effect of both fertility and EGMS genes. Seed multiplication of the CMS line can be done with ease, taking advantage of fertility transformation under low-temperature conditions. To minimize the risk of temperature fluctuations, the CMS line can be planted in alternate rows with its B line. If high temperatures prevail during the seed multiplication phase and make the CMS line completely sterile, the B line as a maintainer can provide abundant pollen for outcrossing. If selfing does occur, it would help to further increase seed yield of the thermosensitive CMS line. ■

Screening rice germplasm for floral attributes that influence outcrossing

S. K. Sahoo, R. Singh, L. C. Prasad, R. M. Singh, D. K. Singh, Genetics and Plant Breeding Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221005; and S. K. Agrawal, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

A cytosterile line with high outcrossing potential would economize the cost of hybrid seed production in rice. We screened rice germplasm to identify genotypes with useful floral traits that could influence outcrossing. We used prospective maintainers and restorers in a testcross nursery program. Isolation of prospective maintainers with useful floral characteristics could lead to the development of cytosterile lines with high outcrossing potential

through a backcrossing program. We evaluated 75 genotypes for floral and related traits: duration of opening of florets, angle of opened florets, percentage of exerted stigma, spikelet length, anther length, stigma length, panicle length, number of effective tillers plant⁻¹, grain yield plant⁻¹, and plant height. The analysis of variance recorded highly significant differences for all the traits, indicating the presence of a sufficient degree of variation for these traits for selection among cultivars. We identified genotypes Aditya, VL Dhan 63, IET10119, IET10115, IET10119, Shankar, VL Dhan 8, Pratibha, Kunti, Surajmukhi, and Vikas as possessing multiple floral traits that would enhance seed set. All these genotypes can therefore be used as parental lines to develop hybrids and enhance outcrossing. ■

Review of notes. The IRRN editor will send an acknowledgment card or an e-mail message when a note is received. An IRRN scientist, selected by the editor, reviews each note. Reviewer names are not disclosed. Depending on the reviewer's report, a note will be accepted for publication, rejected, or returned to the author(s) for revision.

Comments. If you have comments or suggestions about the IRRN, please write to the editor.